

A STUDY OF THE NON-LINEAR BEHAVIOUR OF ADHESIVELY-BONDED COMPOSITE ASSEMBLIES

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SUMMARY: The objective of this study is to define a reliable tool for dimensioning of adhesively bonded assemblies, particularly for marine and underwater applications. A modified Arcan fixture, suited for the study of the behaviour of bonded metal-metal assemblies, was developed in order to focus on the analysis of the behaviour of the adhesive in thin films. To analyze the kinematics of the deformation of the adhesive joint non-contact extensometry techniques were employed. Thus various characteristics of the non-linear behaviour of the adhesive were observed. The first results obtained for mixed assemblies (steel, aluminium, composite substrates) indicate that the “intrinsic” behaviour of the adhesive is obtained using the proposed procedure. Furthermore, quality controls by DSC, and studies of curing by DMA have been performed to verify the bonding procedure.

KEYWORDS: Adhesion, Composite, Marine structures, Arcan fixture, Finite Element, Non-linear behaviour.

INTRODUCTION

Assembly by adhesive bonding [1, 2] offers many advantages and major aerospace projects have addressed its use in aircraft structures, but a lack of confidence currently limits the marine use of this technology. If applications are to be extended it must be clearly demonstrated that the strength of adhesively bonded structures can be predicted accurately. This work is part of an ongoing project aimed at developing numerical tools for adhesively bonded marine structures. Difficulty in modelling the failure of even simple joints (composite/composite lap shear specimens) highlighted the need for more reliable constituent input data [3]. The lap shear specimen is the most widely used geometry for adhesive bonding studies. Specimens such as single lap-shear or double lap-shear joints, are easy to use, but generate strong stress gradients [4, 5]; therefore it is quite difficult to analyse such experiments (Fig. 1).

In a first study, an experimental methodology enabling the adhesives of interest to be characterized up to failure was proposed [6]. A metal-metal assembly was considered, in order to concentrate on the analysis of the behaviour of thin adhesive films. The aims were to characterize the adhesive, analyse its non-linear behaviour, and study the influence of parameters such as film thickness and manufacturing conditions. In order to be able to study the behaviour of the adhesive as a function of the normal stress component, an important parameter, a modified Arcan fixture [7] has been developed, which enables compression or tension to be combined with shear loads. For the epoxy resin Vantico™ Redux 420 the

fracture envelope in the normal stress–shear stress plane has been obtained. We note that compression increases the rupture shear stress at failure significantly. Moreover, the influence of fabrication conditions on the adhesive has been studied through modulated differential scanning calorimetry analysis and dynamical mechanical analysis.

The finer determination of the characteristics of the adhesive requires study and modelling of its non-linear behaviour. To analyse the kinematics of the bonded joint deformation we chose to use non-contact extensometry techniques. Tests carried out for proportional loadings show various characteristics of the behaviour of the adhesive. A model of the non-linear behaviour is under development to represent the evolution of the displacement of the two ends of the bonded joint according to the applied stress. This type of model can be justified by the observation of an homogeneous deformation in the thickness of the joint. As the numerical simulations, performed for linear behaviour, have shown a non uniform evolution of the stress state in the joint, inverse techniques have to be used for identification. The results obtained with steel or aluminium substrates and with mixed assemblies involving composites seem to confirm that the “intrinsic” behaviour of the adhesive is obtained by the procedure suggested.

THE EXPERIMENTAL FIXTURE

In order to be able to study the behaviour of the adhesive as a function of the normal stress component, a modified Arcan fixture has been developed, which enables compression or tension to be combined with shear loads (Fig. 1). Numerical simulations in linear elasticity, for bi-material structures show that the use of a special geometry for the substrate (a beak close to the adhesive joint) makes it possible to eliminate the contribution of the singularities due to edge effects [4, 6]. One wants to obtain the most uniform possible stress field in the adhesive joint and maximum stress in the centre in order to limit the influence of defects. Moreover non linear simulations taking into account the fixing system of the substrates on the supporting fixture were used to optimise the design of the complete fixture in order to prevent pre-loading of the adhesive joint [6].

Fig. 1: Single lap-shear specimen and Arcan type fixtures

To preserve the simplicity associated with the Arcan fixture, and the use of a traditional tensile testing machine, a specimen with rectangular section was proposed taking into account the problems involved in machining (Fig. 2 & 3). The symmetry with respect to the loading plane (O, X, Y), O being the centre of the specimen, and the anti-symmetric loading make it possible to reduce this three-dimensional simulation to one quarter of the specimen by applying adequate boundary conditions. After the simulation of the fastening of the specimen, a tension-shear loading is imposed on the upper face of the support. Under linear behaviour

assumptions, the maximum values of the components of the stress are obtained starting from the finite elements results (Fig. 2) and from the average stress obtained based on the loads measured during the experimental test and the section of the adhesive plane (S_c):

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{yy} \text{ maxi} &= 1.12 \sigma_{yy} \text{ average} \quad \text{with } \sigma_{yy} \text{ average} = F_y / S_c \\ \sigma_{xy} \text{ maxi} &= 1.29 \sigma_{xy} \text{ average} \quad \text{with } \sigma_{xy} \text{ average} = F_x / S_c \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Dimensions of the joint of adhesive being relatively small (70 mm x 10 mm), it is necessary to minimise the parasitic loads [6]; thus an adequate procedure is used to minimise the influence of these defects (use of an assembly fixture, dimensional control and checks...). Moreover, numerical simulations in linear elasticity show that the stresses are not homogeneous through the thickness of the adhesive joint ; but it is important to note that these edge effects are quite small for the specimens with the beak [6].

Fig. 2: Model and numerical results for the specimen with a rectangular section

ANALYSIS OF THE KINEMATICS OF THE BONDED JOINT DEFORMATION

Analysis of displacements in the bonded joint

To analyse the kinematics of the bonded joint deformation we chose to use a non-contact extensometry system based on image correlation [8]. The direct study of displacements and strains in the bonded joint is difficult because its geometry is not flat at the edges of the specimen, the thickness is low (of the order of 0.5 mm), and due to the presence of the beaks. Thus, we study the displacements of both substrates; furthermore, in order to obtain good precision on the displacements, a zone of approximately 1 cm x 1 cm is analysed with images of 1280 pixels x 1024 pixels. Fig. 8 presents the experimental system used in the case of a shear test of the adhesive (90°). For this test the crosshead displacement rate of the tensile testing machine is imposed at 0.5 mm/min and an image is recorded every second. The zone

studied is taken to be symmetric with respect to the adhesive joint to allow an analysis of the displacement of both substrates. Then, after obtaining the displacement fields in both studied zones by image correlation, an optimisation technique is used to obtain the best displacement field of the substrates. This technique was used with a rigid body displacement model for the substrates or with a model taking into account the strains of the substrates associated with tension and shear stresses. The stresses of the aluminium substrates being relatively low both approaches give similar results for the relative displacements of both ends of the adhesive joint. Therefore one obtains a representation of the time evolution of the displacement of the substrates [9]. We denote respectively by DN and DT the relative displacements of both ends of the adhesive joint respectively in the normal and tangential directions in the mean plane of the adhesive joint. FN and FT represent respectively the components of the applied load in the normal and tangential directions to the average plan of the adhesive joint.

Fig. 3: Displacement measurement system & Substrates for bonded assembly

Behaviour of the bonded joint

- (i) monotonic loading
- (ii) cyclic loading

(a) monotonic and cyclic loadings

- (i) monotonic loading
- (ii) 20 cycles at 12 kN and monotonic loading
- (iii) 20 cycles at 13 kN and monotonic loading

(b) cyclic loadings in the "elastic" zone

Fig. 4: Behaviour for shear tests under monotonic and cyclic loadings (90°)

Fig. 4 presents the results of a shear test under monotonic load and under cyclic loading with increasing value of the load. We can note two zones in the adhesive behaviour:

- (a) A first zone which we can consider as "elastic" characterised by a linear relation between the applied load and the displacement DT; this zone is associated with a weak evolution of the strain in the adhesive.
- (b) A second zone with a non-linear behaviour characterised by an important evolution of the strain of the adhesive joint.

Moreover one can notice a viscoplastic behaviour of the adhesive joint. Fig. 4 presents also

the behaviour of the adhesive joint for shear tests under monotonic load and under cyclic loads (20 cycles) in the “elastic” zone followed by a monotonic load. These results show that there are small plastic strains for loads in the so called “elastic” zone behaviour.

Fig. 5: Behaviour for tension-shear tests under monotonic loading

Fig. 6: Behaviour for compression-shear tests under “relaxation” type loading (135°)

Fig. 5 presents, with respect to the angle of the loading to the normal of the main plane of the adhesive, the behaviour of the adhesive in the load-displacement diagram for tension-shear monotonic loading (curves are indicated by the angle). One can note a large tangential displacement DT, when the shear stress is more important than the normal stress (angles from 45° to 90°). Fig. 6 illustrates the behaviour of the adhesive under compression-shear loadings. For “relaxation” type loadings, obtained by blocking the cross-head of the tensile testing machine, we observe an increase of the deformation of the adhesive joint and a decrease of the effort transmitted by the joint. It is also important to notice that the normal component (DN) of the displacement of the adhesive is much lower than the tangential component (DT) (of the order of 1/20 in compression-shear (135°) and 1/10 in traction-shear (45°)).

INVERSE IDENTIFICATION TECHNIQUE OF THE NON LINEAR BEHAVIOUR

A model of the non-linear behaviour is under development to represent the evolution of the displacement of the two ends of the bonded joint according to the applied stress [10]. This type of model can be justified by the observation of an homogeneous deformation in the thickness of the adhesive joint. The idea is to use joint type models in a Finite Element code to simulate the behaviour of structures with bonded joints. This type of element, which uses the displacement of the two ends of the bonded joint and the stress as variables, is able to represent the behaviour of bonded joints by using coarse meshes in the adhesive joint [5]. As the numerical simulations, performed assuming linear behaviour of the constituents, have

shown a non uniform evolution of the state of stress in the adhesive joint, inverse type techniques have to be used to identify the model. The input of the optimisation is the load-displacement curve for the bonded joint presented in the previous chapter. In a first stage, as we are working with the displacement of the two ends of the bonded joint and the stress, it is not necessary to use non linear 3D finite element simulations to perform the optimisation. One can use a simplified approach which verifies the different equations of the problem [11]. This problem can be defined on the mean plane of the adhesive and one can use the elastic stress distribution (Fig. 2) as initial value ; therefore a nearly classical non linear time dependent problem has to be solved. The first tests have been made for the case of shear tests under monotonic loading. For such loadings, the use of a plastic behaviour with isotropic hardening (fig. 7-b) gives good results: fig. 7-a presents the experiment curve and the numerical one. Fig. 7-c represents the shear stress with respect to the segment [OX] (Fig. 2) for different values of the loading. One can note the elastic response for a low load (a,b), a nearly uniform stress field before rupture (d, e) and an intermediate distribution in the transition part (c).

Fig. 7: Result of the inverse identification for a shear test under monotonic loading

This inverse identification technique must be applied to other loading conditions and a model has to be developed to represent the behaviour of the bonded joint presented in the previous chapter (viscoelastic and viscoplastic behaviour, [12, 13]). Moreover the “elastic” yield surface, presented in the following chapter has to be taken into account.

STRENGTH ENVELOPE IN TERMS OF STRESSES

Fig. 8-a presents, in the normal stress–shear stress plane, the fracture envelope obtained for the epoxy resin Vantico Redux 420 during the tests intended to validate the whole test procedure. The adhesive was left for 12 hours at 20°C after assembly then cured at 50°C for 4 hours. These results are obtained with a thickness of the adhesive joint of 0.4mm ± 0.02 and an imposed displacement rate of 0.5 mm/minute. The previous analysis of the non-linear response of the bonded joint shows that near rupture one can assume that the stress is nearly constant in the middle plane of the adhesive joint. Thus the fracture envelope is plotted with the average stresses. The behaviour observed is interesting, a strength (based on maximum stress) under normal tension near and even slightly higher than that under shear loading is noted. Moreover compression increases the rupture shear stress of the adhesive joint at failure significantly, which is very important for underwater applications (Fig. 8-b). The examination of fracture surfaces shows an adhesive-cohesive type failure when the normal stress is dominant and a mixed-cohesive type failure when the shear stress is dominant. For practical use of the strength envelope in terms of stresses it seems useful to determine the “elastic” domain; this is plotted with the maximum values of the stresses computed under elastic assumptions (equation (1)).

(a) fracture envelope

(b) "elastic" and fracture envelopes

Fig. 8: Tension/compression-shear fracture and "elastic" envelopes, Vantico Redux 420

INFLUENCE OF FABRICATION CONDITIONS ON THE ADHESIVE

(a) DSC results for cure quality check

(b) influence of post-cure, DMA

Fig. 9: Example of DSC and DMA analysis

Modulated Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was used to check the adhesive cure. Samples were cured in the oven at the same time as the Arcan assemblies and were scanned at 5°C/minute. Fig. 9-a shows an example of the results. The arrow indicates the start of the glass transition region and this is around 40°C after a 4 hours 50°C cure. The non-reversible heat flow indicates that cure is not complete but continues during the temperature ramp. Higher cure temperatures can be used to increase T_g but in a boatyard environment low temperature cures are more common. The advantage of this method is that only very small quantities are required, but it gives little information on the mechanical behaviour of the adhesive. Dynamical mechanical analysis is a complementary technique enabling the adhesive viscoelastic behaviour to be studied under low mechanical loads. Films of adhesive were cast between thick polymer plates at the same time as the DSC samples and subjected to small sinusoidal displacements at 1 Hz. Tests were performed on 10 mm wide 1 mm thick strips in tension. Fig. 9-b shows an example which indicates the difference between a room temperature cure and curing for 4 hours at 50°C. There is a strong viscoelastic response at room temperature, related to the low T_g, and this suggests that rate effects will need to be considered in the characterisation of this adhesive. This also underlines the importance of

Careful control of curing conditions.

STUDY OF MIXED ASSEMBLIES

Influence of the substrate material

The results obtained with steel substrates (Fig. 10) show that the nature of the substrates has very little influence on the analysis of the behaviour of the adhesive. However it is important to note that an adequate preparation of surfaces must be carried out for each material. In order to analyze the behaviour of mixed bonding with composite, a validation test was carried out. A plate of composite (three plies of composite $0^\circ/90^\circ$ with high resistance carbon of 193 g/m^2 and epoxy resin SR1500) was bonded between two aluminium substrates. For a traction-shear loading (45°) a rupture by delamination of the composite was obtained for a rather small relative displacement of the substrates, but of the same order of magnitude as that obtained for a joining with metal substrates. Fig. 11 presents the rupture mode of the composite and a section through a mixed bonded shows the thicknesses of the composite and the two joints. It should be noted that there are two joints and that the level of failure load is rather low in the presence of the composite. Additional tests are underway out to confirm these first results.

Fig. 10: Influence of the substrate material

Fig. 11: Test of mixed bonding with composite (traction-shear at 45°)

Nevertheless, the first results obtained for the mixed bonding (steel, aluminium, composite) indicate that the “intrinsic” behaviour of the adhesive is obtained using the proposed procedure.

Influence of the thickness of the bonded joint and influence of the loading rate

For some applications, in a boatyard environment, it is nearly impossible to obtain a bonded joint with a regular thickness. An example, in the case of racing yachts, is the assembly of the sail guide rail to a composite mast where the rail is several metres long. In order to be able to optimise such assemblies, different tests were carried out with different of the bondline thicknesses. Fig. 12 presents the results for two batches of specimens under shear monotonic loading: the first one involves adhesive made after the first opening of a pot (“new” adhesive), the second is with a so-called “old” adhesive and was made some weeks after the opening the adhesive pack. For these diagrams one uses the tangential displacement normalised with the thickness of the bonded joint. The “elastic” deformation is proportional to the thickness of the joint and an increase of the joint thickness reduces the failure load. A possible explanation is an increase of the defects (air bubble , ...) with joint thickness. Moreover one can note an “ageing” of the adhesive before preparation after the first opening of a pot, in terms of mechanical properties (property observed on different batches of adhesive). The analysis of the cure kinetics of different adhesives (isothermal cure at 50°) underline the results (Fig. 13-a). This again underlines the importance of careful control of curing conditions. Moreover, Fig. 13-b presents, for a loading of tension-shear (45°), the behaviour of the adhesive for various cross-head loading rates. A weak dependence on the loading rate is observed.

Fig 12: Behaviour for shear tests under monotonic loading with different joint thicknesses

Fig. 13: Degree of conversion of adhesive & Influence of the loading rate (tension-shear, 45°)

CONCLUSION

The objective of this study is to develop tools able to predict the behaviour of adhesively bonded assemblies for marine structures. The development of an Arcan type fixture, with a beak making it possible to limit the edge effects, coupled with non-contact extensometry techniques allows a reliable analysis of the kinematics of the deformation of the joint of the

adhesive in an assembly. Experimental results are presented, for a 0.4 mm thick epoxy adhesive and these show a strong positive influence of compression on assembly strength. Tension/compression-shear fracture and “elastic” envelopes have been determined and various aspects of the non-linear behaviour of the adhesive were observed for radial loadings. In particular, creep or relaxation conditions has a large influence on the behaviour of the joint. These analyses have to be developed to enable the full non-linear stress-displacement behaviour to be determined. The identification of this model is underway starting from inverse techniques, and the first results are encouraging. The results obtained for mixed assembly seem to show that the “intrinsic” behaviour of the adhesive is obtained by the procedure suggested. Moreover the influence of the various fabrication conditions of the adhesive joint (cure procedure, thickness of the joint ...) have been studied. This work is continuing to develop the full non-linear stress-displacement behaviour model, in order to allows us to analyse the behaviour of industrial adhesively bonded assemblies for marine structures.

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